

Appendix C: Survey Questions

Section A: Company & Product

1. Which categories describe your company? (Select all that apply)
Chipset vendor; SDK/platform provider; OEM/ODM; White-label manufacturer; Consumer brand; Other
2. Which markets do you sell to? (Select all that apply)
China; Asia; Middle East; Europe; North America; Other
3. Which product categories do you manufacture? (Select all that apply)
Smart cameras; Smartwatches; Home smart devices (plugs, lights, sensors); Smart appliances; Industrial IoT; Other
4. Approximate number of IoT SKUs your company maintains per year:
1-20; 21-50; 50+
5. Do your products currently support OTA firmware updates?
Yes, all products; Yes, some products; No
6. Company size and R&D team size:
1-20; 21-50; 50+

Section B: OTA Update Frequency & History

1. How frequently do you release OTA firmware updates for a typical product?
Weekly; Monthly; Quarterly; 1-2 times per year; Only for critical issues; Never
2. What typically triggers an OTA release? (Select all that apply)
Security vulnerabilities; New features; Bug fixes; Compliance requirements; Customer complaints; Platform or partner requirements; Other
3. What percentage of deployed devices receive OTA updates within 30 days?
≥90%; 70-90%; 40-70%; <40%; Unknown

Section C: OTA Development Effort & Timeline

1. How long does it take to prepare a typical OTA update?
<1 week; 1-4 weeks; 1-3 months; ≥3 months
2. Approximate engineering effort per OTA release (person-days):
<5; 5-20; 20-60; 60+; Not tracked
3. Do you depend on upstream vendors (chipset or SDK providers) for OTA-related changes?
Yes, always; Yes, sometimes; Rarely; Never
4. Average time required to receive patches from upstream vendors:
<1 week; 1-4 weeks; 1-3 months; No formal support
5. How often do integration or build failures delay OTA updates?
Frequently; Sometimes; Rarely; Never

Section D: OTA Delivery Infrastructure & Security

1. How do you deliver OTA updates? (Select all that apply)
Vendor-managed OTA server; Third-party platform (Tuya, Espressif, Quectel, etc.); CDN hosting (HTTP/HTTPS); App-assisted updates; Manual (USB, cable); Other
2. Which security measures are used in OTA delivery? (Select all that apply)
Firmware signing; TLS encryption; Incremental/delta updates; Anti-rollback; Secure boot; None; Not sure
3. Approximate OTA failure rate during deployment:
<1%; 1-5%; ≥5%; Unknown
4. Can you remotely view OTA success/failure statistics?
Yes; No

Section E: Economic & Organizational Factors

1. Rank the reasons for providing OTA updates:
Security compliance; Product improvements; Reduce support costs; Customer expectations; Required by distributors/platforms; Other
2. Rank the barriers to releasing OTA updates more frequently:
Engineering cost; Lack of staff; Dependency on upstream vendors; Testing burden; Risk of bricking devices; Logistical challenges; Low profit margins; Other
3. Estimated cost per OTA update lifecycle (development + testing + delivery):

4. Would you offer more OTA updates if cost and effort were lower?
Yes; No; Unsure

Section F: Product Lifecycle & End-of-Support

1. Typical lifecycle of a product without OTA:
1 year; 1-2 years; 2-3 years; 3-5 years; >5 years
2. How long do you continue issuing OTA updates after product launch?
6 months; 6-12 months; 1-2 years; 2-3 years; Entire product lifetime; Case-by-case
3. Rank reasons for ending OTA support:
Hardware limitations; Low sales volume; Upstream vendor stops supporting; Cost constraints; Replaced by newer models; Other